

RESEARCH ON NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL AGING: A NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH

Iskanderova Sayyora Abdubasidovna

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences Teacher of the
Department of Psychology

***Annotation:** The current state of views on mental aging is characterized by a refusal to understand it solely as a time of “losses”. The concepts of complexity, inconsistency and non-linearity of the changes taking place in the systems of vital activity, including the psyche, are replacing them.*

***Keywords:** normal and abnormal aging, cognitive sphere, neuropsychological approach, Alzheimer's disease, method.*

INTRODUCTION

As is known, aging is a natural process, accompanied by characteristic age-related changes in organs and systems, leading to a limitation of the body's adaptive capabilities, which can be compensated during normal aging. In this regard, we can say that mental aging is characterized not by impairments, but by features of the cognitive sphere.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Limitations in the cognitive sphere are associated primarily with changes in the nervous system in general and in the brain in particular. In the most general form, these changes are represented by a decrease in brain mass (death of neurons, demyelination of pathways, smoothing of the sulci and convolutions, expansion of the subarachnoid spaces and cerebral ventricles when they are filled with cerebrospinal fluid). There is evidence of a decrease in the number of neurons in some areas of the brain by 45% by the age of 90 [4]. In the cognitive sphere, for this reason, the so-called age-related symptoms appear, which are observed in such mental functions as memory, attention, perception, etc. All this determines the

adequacy of the neurocognitive approach in relation to the analysis of mental activity during aging.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding the features of cognitive activity during normal aging requires consideration of several provisions.

1. Along with age-related symptoms of limitations in adaptive capabilities, there are compensatory positive phenomena of the regulation of mental activity in the changed conditions of life. This conclusion is supported by the adaptive-regulatory concept (V.V.Frolkis), according to which natural compensatory mechanisms exist in all life systems. In this context, it is increasingly being said that the restrictions that come with age should be considered not as disorders leading to regression, but as special age-related symptoms that can be overcome and corrected [1].

All of the above allows us to introduce the concept of “late ontogeny”, associated with the appearance in the psyche and behavior of something new that was not at the previous stages of life (L.S.Vygotsky).

2. At a later age, the main laws of development, characteristic of earlier periods of ontogenesis, continue to operate: heterochrony, heterotopy, heterodynamism of changes in the psyche. We are talking about the fact that the components of the psyche change at different times, different mental functions are characterized by different sensitivity to the influence of disadaptive factors and different rates of change [2].

3. In aging, restrictions to one degree or another affect almost all mental processes: memory, attention, speech, thinking, perception, processing of visual-spatial information. These cognitive functions have a complex structural organization within which changes can be uneven due to the developmental laws mentioned above [3].

4. The implementation of the neuropsychological approach is most effectively ensured, in our opinion, by applying the concept of A.R. Luria about 3 functional blocks of the brain (FBB) [4].

Each of the 3 FBBs is represented symmetrically in the left and right hemispheres of the brain, which are specific in their leading role in cognitive processes. At the same time, the optimal implementation of the latter requires the joint work of the hemispheres, which is provided by the cerebral commissures (in particular, the corpus callosum).

5. An important parameter of normal aging is its individuality. The role of physiological and mental development preceding aging is as great as genetic information, the amount, type and duration of exposure to risk factors and somatic diseases. Very significant are emotional and personal characteristics, readiness to consciously and responsibly cope with new life circumstances, the structure of cognitive activity, professional knowledge and skills, equipment with strategies for regulating behavior, and features of cognitive styles.

Memory disorders in most cases are leading in the structure of the syndrome already at the initial stage of the disease. Patients show inefficiency in learning a verbal sequence, often stagnant reproduction of the same words, contamination (indiscriminate recall of words from previous tasks). An additional load in the form of hetero- and homogeneous interference can lead to complete forgetting of the stimulus material.

The semantic organization of the latter (memorization of phrases) helps to improve reproduction, but only in relation to short (3-4 words) phrases. The same features of memorization are also observed in relation to visual and other stimuli. This indicates that memory disorders are modally nonspecific [7-8].

The second component of the syndrome includes such symptoms as impaired optical-spatial functions, nominative function of speech, kinetic, kinesthetic and spatial organization of movements, as well as visual gnosis in tasks to distinguish a figure from the background. These disorders are accompanied by difficulties in understanding speech (with the preservation of phonemic hearing), which arise either with an increase in the volume of the speech task, or in the case of using rare or grammatically complicated words as stimuli, or in the case of a specific logical-grammatical construction of the phrase [9-10].

Patients with the presenile type of Alzheimer's disease often make mistakes when performing counting operations in oral and written forms (errors when passing through a dozen, spatial errors). The operations of addition and multiplication are relatively more preserved than subtractions and divisions; there are difficulties in remembering the multiplication table.

Summarizing the data concerning the second component of the neuropsychological syndrome in the presenile type of Alzheimer's disease indicates a particular severity of symptoms characteristic of the pathology of the parietal, parietal-occipital, premotor regions, as well as extranuclear regions of the left temporal lobe of the brain. We are talking about a pronounced and widespread lesion of the second block of the brain, to a much greater extent affecting the left hemispheric structures included in it [11-12]. In our opinion, this is precisely what prevents the actualization of compensatory mechanisms in the sphere of mental activity, which leads to a high degree of severity of disorders of mental functions.

The third block of the brain (frontal prefrontal regions) at the initial stage of the presenile type of Alzheimer's disease remains more functionally intact than the first and especially the second. Such heterochrony leads to a fairly long-term preservation of the “personality façade”, some regulatory functions, emotional response to a disease, and the availability of a number of well-automated skills fixed in past experience [5].

The leading component of the syndrome indicates dysfunction of the first energy block of the brain (narrowing of the volume of mental activity or limitation in its multichannel nature, memory impairment due to pathological inhibition of traces by interfering influences, impairment of neurodynamic components in the motor sphere).

The second component of the syndrome is represented by a complex of symptoms indicating a decrease in voluntary control in various higher mental functions: echopraxia, reduction or loss of the program of the initiated action, the presence of contamination, paraphasias and confabulations in tasks for memorization and reproduction, replacement of a holistic and generalized

understanding of the plot picture by a fragmentary enumeration of its details, paragnosia, impulsiveness when performing “reaction of choice” tests, a decrease in the controlling and regulating role of speech in building programs of movements and actions. These symptoms are associated with disturbances in the work of the prefrontal sections (block 3) of the brain.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the picture of cognitive disorders in Alzheimer's disease, on the one hand, symptoms characteristic of normal aging (decrease in the functions of the first FBB) can be distinguished, which are presented to a more pronounced degree and steadily progress in the course of the disease. On the other hand, characteristic of Alzheimer's disease and most different from the norm is the impairment of functions provided by the left hemisphere of the brain in the form of successive (stage-by-stage, unfolded in time) processing of information, which is provided by the second FBB. It can be seen that with an increase in clinical symptoms, the ability to regulate activity (3rd FBB) is also greatly reduced, which leads to almost complete failure of patients. Thus, in Alzheimer's disease, all 3 FBBs are involved in the pathological process, which prevents the actualization of even minimal compensatory capabilities [6].

All of the above about the features of both normal and pathological aging, based on the use of a neuropsychological approach, allows us to draw a conclusion about the prospects for the formation of psychological support strategies for aging people using correctional programs aimed at optimizing cognitive functioning.

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